

USE OF STATISTICAL AND ECONOMETRIC MODELS IN CREDIT RISK ANALYSIS

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Abstract: Risk control of banks has social significance. Disruptions in the banking sector have a negative impact on the entire economy. What's more, they cause significant social upheavals (let's remember the "pyramid banks" in our country from the beginning of the 90s). The question is both from the point of view of economic development and from the aspect of profitability of the bank itself, how high can bank placements be and how much risk can be taken in order not to jeopardize the security of the bank's obligations. Banking risks are credit, market, currency, solvency risk and operational risk. The paper deals with the oldest of financial risks - credit risk. If there is something that unites the renaissance banker sitting at the bench with money - "banco" and the risk analyst in the high-rise of Wall Street, then it is credit risk. The oldest, but still the most important risk. Today, thanks to modern computer technology, the archiving of databases, the movement of parameter values in the past, it is possible to predict the risks taken. Credit risk is observed at the level of an individual credit line - standalone risk, or in concentration - portfolio credit risk. In order to establish the relationship between the risk of the total exposure and the capital of the bank, which is the last line of defense of solvency, by the G7 countries, the Basel standards were promoted. Credit risk parameters are the basic tools for risk monitoring. The default rate, and the loss due to default, are derived based on

Keywords: Statistical models, econometric models, credit risk, credit score, default liability, lender.